

ANALYSIS OF POETRY PRACTICE BASED ON APPRECIATION
AND TRANSLATION<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10335979>**PhD Amanguli YIMING,**Associate Professor, Xinjiang Agricultural University,
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Abstract. *The article emphasizes the necessity of poetry practice and strategy optimization. At the same time, taking poetry appreciation and poetry translation as the starting points, a series of modern poetry translation optimization strategies are proposed, including analyzing the author's life and writing background in advance, guiding readers to recite and appreciate the entire poem, and implementing multi-dimensional deepening analysis of the entire poem encourage readers to imitate and create modern poetry, guide readers to appreciate multiple translated versions, and carry out poetry translation practice. This emphasizes the key points of poetry practice based on appreciation and translation, in order to accelerate the upgrading of modern poetry translation.*

Keywords: poetry appreciation, poetry translation, modern Poetry

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada she'riyat amaliyoti va strategiyani optimallashtirish zarurligi ta'kidlangan. Shu bilan birga, she'riyatni qadrlash va uning tarjimasini boshlang'ich nuqta sifatida olib, zamonaviy she'riyat tarjimasini optimallashtirish strategiyalari taklif etiladi, jumladan, muallifning hayoti va yozilish tarixini oldindan tahlil qilib, o'quvchilarni butun she'rni o'qish va qadrlashga yo'naltirish hamda butun she'rning ko'p qirrali chuqur tahlilini amalga oshirgan holda o'quvchilarni taqlid qilish va zamonaviy she'r yaratishga undaydi, o'quvchilarni bir nechta tarjima variantlarini qadrlashga va she'r tarjimasini amaliyotini amalga oshirishga yordam beradi. Bu zamonaviy she'riyat tarjimasini yuksaltirishni jadallashtirish maqsadida qadrlash va tarjimaga asoslangan she'riyat amaliyotining asosiy nuqtalariga urg'u beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: she'riyatni qadrlash, she'r tarjimasini, zamonaviy she'riyat

Аннотация. *В статье подчеркивается необходимость оптимизации поэтической практики и стратегии. В то же время, взяв за отправную точку оценку и перевод поэзии, предлагается ряд современных стратегий оптимизации перевода поэзии, включая предварительный анализ жизни автора и его писательского опыта, наставляя читателей прочитать и*

оценить все стихотворение, а также внедрение многомерного углубленного анализа всего стихотворения, побуждая читателей подражать и создавать современную поэзию, наставлять читателей в оценке несколько переведенных версий и в практике перевода стихов. Это подчеркивает ключевые моменты поэтической практики, основанной на оценке и переводе, чтобы ускорить совершенствование современного перевода поэзии.

Ключевые слова: *оценка поэзии, перевод поэзии, современная поэзия*

Introduction. At present, optimizing and implementing the update of modern poetry strategies is an inevitable choice to improve the actual teaching quality level. In practice, modern poetry strategies can be adjusted from two aspects: appreciation and translation, in order to achieve more ideal teaching effects.

A. The Necessity Analysis of Poetry Practice and Strategy Optimization. With the proposal of core literacy, the cultivation of readers' core literacy has attracted people's attention. Chinese language teaching activities are to some extent aesthetic activities. Through modern poetry translation activities to cultivate readers' aesthetic appreciation and creativity, it has a positive significance for cultivating a capital "person", mastering the characteristics of poetry, and exploring potential information "hidden literary value, storage poetry value ". To accommodate a large number of visual and emotional elements in a limited space, a poem must maximize the potential information through its explicit information. The more outstanding a poet is, the more emphasis they place on the connotation of their poetry. That is to say, the better a poem, the more hidden information it contains and can be organically combined. In terms of poetry, there are generally two types of internal information: image and emotion. Like other literary works, the objects written in poetry are not external to people, events, objects, scenery, or emotions, but due to their concise language and highly concentrated content. So, there are a large number of people, things, scenery (images), and emotions hidden outside of the literal meaning, which we call latent information. The potential image information mainly includes scenery features and lyrical subjects (characters). When appreciating poetry, scenery is our inevitable focus. The scenery written by the poet as external explicit information is the key to capturing latent information.

In the context of reader theory, strengthening reader quality education is a common goal pursued by the whole society and writer. For Chinese language and literature teaching, corresponding teaching reforms should also be carried out to improve its teaching quality. Poetry appreciation teaching, as a key content of Chinese language classrooms, can not only stimulate readers' interest and

enthusiasm in learning Chinese, but also enhance readers' Chinese literacy. Based on this, this article mainly explores optimization strategies for poetry translation.

B. Analysis of Optimization Strategies for Modern Poetry Based on Appreciation. (1) Analysis of the author's life and writing background. Before leading readers to delve deeper into modern poetry, writers or teachers can approach it from the perspective of poetry appreciation, allowing readers or readers to fully understand the content and emotional connotations of modern poetry. In practice, teachers can guide readers to analyze the poet, creative styles, and life stories of modern poetry works, allowing readers to interpret the emotions and themes of modern poetry works from the perspective of poets.

During this process, teachers can allow readers to complete preliminary reading of modern poetry works in small groups before class, as well as collect and organize relevant materials, including the author's life story, the background of poetry writing, and so on. Each group chooses an angle, organizes relevant materials, and creates a PowerPoint presentation for presentation and sharing at the beginning of the class. Relying on such teaching design, readers can better grasp important information related to modern poetry works, provide strong support for the deepening of practical modern poetry teaching and in-depth interpretation of content, reduce the difficulty of modern poetry appreciation, and improve the effectiveness of modern poetry teaching.

(2) Appreciation and Recitation of the Whole Poem

Modern poetry teaching is an important link in implementing aesthetic education and improving language proficiency in Chinese language teaching. However, in practical teaching, the phenomenon of "inability to understand" and "inability to speak well" still exists, leading to readers losing interest in learning modern poetry. Today, with the popularization of information technology 2.0, teachers can create scenarios through multimedia, and through methods such as sound, pictures, music, and videos, let readers experience the imagery and artistic conception in poetry from multiple perspectives. Poets are all created for the perception of objects, reflecting the soul. Therefore, understanding the author and writing background can help readers grasp the emotional tone of poetry as a whole; We should also use various forms of reading aloud to make readers feel the language beauty of poetry. Understanding and guiding imagination through reading; We can also carry out poetry imitation, apply what we have learned, enhance readers' comprehensive Chinese literature, and cultivate emotions for protecting nature, loving their family, and defending the motherland. Focusing on recitation, focusing on key words to deeply interpret poetry content, and practicing writing skills in

literature learning; Grasping the structure and sentence structure characteristics of poetry for teaching, classroom practice should start with sentence structure to provide pragmatic training for readers; Poetry teaching should focus on emotional and humanistic aspects to create warmth in literature learning.

In practice, teachers should focus on using beautiful voices like spring breeze and rain to lead readers to repeatedly read and feel the language beauty of poetry. They should also use exquisite courseware to patiently and meticulously guide readers to engage in rich associations and imagination, allowing them to experience the beauty of poetry in real life, making silent words emotional, and making limited language full of vitality. Based on this, unconsciously reading, readers are intoxicated with the artistic conception of poetry, and their aesthetic ability and Chinese language literacy have been improved. At the same time, teachers can use the main images or pictures depicting things that appear in modern poetry works to display through multimedia, allowing readers to talk about their initial impressions. Then, they can lead readers to listen to videos and read aloud, circle new words, clear obstacles to new words, and use various forms of reading aloud, such as model reading, personal reading, train driving reading, and group reading for male and female readers, to help readers understand, taste language, and appreciate writing methods. Pay attention to guiding, encouraging, and appreciating readers in the classroom, ignite their passion for learning modern poetry with enthusiasm, and further encourage readers in the class to change from not daring to speak to daring to speak. The readers' voices become more beautiful and confident.

(3) Multidimensional Deepening Analysis of the Whole Poetry

By setting main questions around the content of modern poetry and drive it throughout the entire learning. Through methods such as situational creation, emotional reading, and classical image analysis, teachers can guide readers to delve deeper into the text, taste and feel the rich imagery, beautiful language, and deep emotions contained in poetry, thereby enhancing readers' thinking operation, aesthetic experience, and cultural influence in poetry reading and learning. During this period, teachers need to fully mobilize readers' learning enthusiasm and taste the poet's emotions through in-depth analysis of imagery. Teachers are required to fully grasp the teaching materials, build harmonious teacher-student interaction, pay attention to guiding readers' learning methods, and encourage personalized reading experiences for readers. Xu Zhimo's new poetry is influenced by Western sonnets, and its style and rhythm are worthy of further research. At the same time, teachers can use the core imagery of modern poetry works as a starting point, advance with a problem-based framework, fully pay attention to the learning status of each student,

encourage and support outstanding readers, and have a strong student attitude and awareness. Poetry has no clear interpretation, and the transmission of literary sentiment is like an iceberg theory. It cannot be confined to literal terms, but must strive to dig deeper, constantly collide, and explore the most valuable connotations and teaching gains.

At the same time, teachers can guide readers to combine the early recitation and recall of poetry content, starting from the overall perspective, and clarifying the overall structure of poetry; Grasp key words and let readers combine their own life experiences, and share daily life and life experiences with modern poetry content; Using group collaborative learning to explore the connotation and meaning of poetry, readers can experience and comprehend through comparison, deepen understanding, and break through teaching difficulties; Small practice writing - to imitate modern poetry and ensure that readers have sufficient time to start writing, in order to ensure good writing results. Teaching should start with fundamental goals, promote developmental goals, achieve ontological goals, and achieve rational goals in parallel, allowing Chinese language to return to its essence. In addition, during the practical teaching of modern poetry from the perspective of appreciation, teachers need to focus on grasping the following key points: recitation as the main focus, enriching the form of reading; Combining reading and writing, carefully designing the points of "writing"; Expand from multiple perspectives to make poetry teaching content more diverse and open.

(4) Encourage readers to imitate and create modern poetry

For readers, there are generally few modern poetry works that they can come into contact with in their actual learning and life. Therefore, their actual poetry appreciation and creative abilities remain at a low level, which is not conducive to the optimization of modern poetry teaching. Based on this, from the perspective of appreciation, during the actual teaching of modern poetry, teachers can focus on encouraging the imitation and creation of modern poetry.

In practice, teachers can teach readers writing skills related to poetry defamiliarization, allowing them to combine the skills they have learned and create imitations based on modern poetry works. Driven by the nature of poetry, new poetry will use techniques such as line breaks, spaces, and punctuation to establish an external form (and also a sound form) for new poetry. The essence of line transitions, blank lines, spaces, and punctuation is a pause. A pause will prolong the reader's perception time, which is the sense of defamiliarization beauty. The beauty of poetry defamiliarization stems from the secrets of poetry branches. The branches of modern poetry can be divided into three categories based on the situation of

sentence pauses: first, sentences cross lines. A complete sentence is cross line. If you haven't finished writing on the previous line, go to the top grid of the second line and continue writing. Secondly, stop in the sentence. Suddenly stop in a complete sentence, usually leaving a blank space before continuing to write. Thirdly, starting from the middle of the line. It can be divided into two situations: ending in the middle of a line and starting in the middle of a line, where the previous sentence ends and the next sentence begins.

Mary Oliver once said, "To write good poetry, one must read extensively and deeply. Excellent poetry is the best teacher, perhaps the only one." Adonis also said, "Imitation is the easiest, and I would like to imitate the sea." Professor Zhou Qixing said, "To write short poetry, seize the moment of inspiration and write the essence of poetry. Based on this, when guiding readers in the creation of modern poetry imitation, they can summarize and impart the "Romantic Quartet" of modern poetry creation, as follows:

Step: to think of a picture or a daily object. For example: ice cream in summer, long figures under streetlights... Choose any thing and write it down. Only by writing it down can poetry occur.

Step 2: describe it in a novel way. Use adjectives that are as 'illegal' as possible. That is, don't mix according to common sense. For example, ice cream has a mustard flavor... its elongated figure weighs a thousand pounds... If you dare not use or even imagine any combination of words, you can freely use it here. This can surprise people's hearts, brighten their eyes, and be unimaginable.

Step 3: end with an emotional sentence. For example, ice cream has a mustard flavor that reminds me of the summer when you left. The heavy figure weighed a thousand pounds, which made me gasp for breath. At this moment, poetry has been born, only due to the east wind.

Step 4: Complete this poem using lines, spaces, blank lines, punctuation, and other methods. For example:

*Ice cream has a mustard smell that reminds me of you
The summer when I left
A figure weighing a thousand pounds
I can't breathe under the pressure*

By organizing readers to learn modern poetry writing skills, as well as training in imitation and creation, it can further deepen readers' understanding of modern poetry works, enhance their ability to appreciate modern poetry, and provide strong support for the optimization of modern poetry writing teaching.

C. Analysis of Optimization Strategies for Modern Poetry Based on Translation

(1) Lead readers to appreciate multiple translated versions

The same poem will form versions with certain differences after being translated by different people. In practical modern poetry teaching, teachers can provide readers with multiple famous translations of the same poem, providing support for further appreciation of modern poetry, and guiding them to exert the translator's subjective initiative, allowing readers to translate their own style.

During this period, teachers need to lead readers to focus on the comparison and appreciation of the original poem and its translation, and combine timely reminders to enable readers to clearly understand the differences between different translators and translated versions in handling the same details in the same poem, analyze the differences and similarities, and understand that modern poetry translation has a high degree of subjectivity, which is a subjective secondary creation of "different opinions". At the same time, teachers can encourage readers to boldly try out translations based on the appreciation of modern poetry works and comparative analysis of multiple translated versions, forming more personal style translations, in order to expand the form and content of modern poetry teaching and accelerate the upgrading of modern poetry teaching.

(2) Teaching and Practice of Poetry Translation

Translating poetry in any language will encounter the same dilemma. This dilemma often lies not in the language itself, but in the uncertainty of the content of the poem itself. When translating modern poetry, we often encounter several problems: firstly, there are many rhetorical devices and meanings in Chinese native language that do not correspond to each other in foreign languages. Secondly, in terms of grammar, some foreign languages have overly rich verb tenses, as well as onomatopoeic and mimetic forms. Thirdly, the absence of some foreign language subjects makes the ambiguity and uncertainty of their poetry even stronger. Based on this situation, during the process of guiding readers to translate modern poetry, it is necessary not to use rigid and dogmatic literal translation, but also to avoid easily infringing on the original text and engaging in additive translation in an extraneous manner. Correspondingly, it is necessary to make some technical and contextual revisions in order to coordinate the content and emotions of poetry.

During the actual translation of modern poetry, it is common to encounter situations where the widely recognized 'first-class poets' cannot be effectively translated into other languages. Specifically, although some poems have received high praise in our country, they cannot withstand the scrutiny of translation due to their closed nature, lack of universality, and lack of relevance to the vast external world and universe, resulting in an empty abstraction and personal sentimentality.

And truly high-quality poetry is translatable, and the good universal spirit and artistic atmosphere of its original work will not be much inferior when translated into other languages. Therefore, poetry that cannot withstand the test of time and translation cannot be called a first-class text. The uncertainty of the content of poetry itself, the ambiguity and emotional nature of some foreign languages, and other factors can easily lead to difficulties in translation. Just as a hundred readers will have a hundred Hamlets, the understanding and translation of modern poetry will also have ten people and ten colors. Based on this, teachers should lead readers to compare and analyze different translated versions of the same modern poem, teach modern poetry translation skills, and guide readers to implement personalized translation of modern poetry on this basis, in order to further deepen their understanding of modern poetry works.

Summary. In summary, optimizing and implementing the update of modern poetry translation strategies is an inevitable choice to improve the actual reading quality level. In practice, we can start from two aspects: poetry appreciation and poetry translation. During the actual modern poetry teaching period, we can analyze the author's life and writing background in advance, organize readers to recite and appreciate the entire poem, implement multi-dimensional deepening analysis of the entire poem, encourage readers to imitate and create modern poetry, support readers to appreciate multiple translated versions, and carry out poetry translation teaching and practice, Improve the quality and effectiveness of modern poetry translation, and promote the upgrading of modern poetry translation.

REFERENCES:

- [1] – Hu Yifan An Analysis of the Teaching Practice of German Poetry Based on Appreciation and Translation - Taking Holdrin's "Half of a Floating Life" as an Example [J] Journal of Zhejiang University of Science and Technology, 2019,31 (02): 152-157.
- [2] – Pan Xiaoyun A Micro Exploration of Foreign Poetry Appreciation from the Perspective of Comparative Reading: Taking the Teaching of "To the Skylark" as an Example [J] Journal: Chinese Literature of middle school 2023, (17): 30-31.
- [3] – Huang Juanhua Foreign Poetry Teaching Focusing on Culture and Aesthetics - Appreciation of the Ministerial Excellent Course "To the Sea" [J] Chinese Language Teaching Communication, 2023, (07): 54-58.
- [4] – Huang Juanhua Teaching Foreign Poetry from the Perspective of Reception Aesthetics - Appreciation of the Ministerial Excellent Course "Trees and the Sky" [J] Chinese Language Teaching Communication, 2023, (07): 58-61.

[5] – Guo Huizhen A Study on the Teaching Path of Chinese Poetry Reading in Middle School: Taking the Teaching of “If Life Deceives You” as an Example [J] National Language Teaching and Research, 2022, (09): 113-115.

